

pharmaceutical dosage forms, such as UV spectrophotometer and HPLC techniques. U.V spectrophotometry and HPLC procedures are the analytical techniques published for the measurement of MONT and BILA both separately and when combined with other medications⁸⁻³⁷. A thorough and in-depth literary analysis reveals that no spectrophotometric method is mentioned in pharmaceutical preparations for the prediction of Montelukast sodium and Bilastine. The goal of this research was to design and validate a spectrophotometric analytical method for the combined prediction of both compounds. According to the ICH criteria, the suggested approach has been optimised and validated.³⁸ In the current work, an attempt has been made to quantify both medications simultaneously utilising the UV spectrophotometer's absorption correction approach. The goal of this study is to be helpful for routine quality control of Montelukast sodium and Bilastine in pharmaceutical formulation.

Figure 1: Structure of Montelukast

Figure 2: Structure of Bilastine

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

EQUIPMENTS

On a UV double beam spectrophotometer, a 1 cm quartz cell was used for the estimation (UV-1700, Shimadzu Corp., Japan). Every chemical's absorption range was also taken into account. Utilizing a Shimadzu Electronic balance, the weighing was conducted (AX 200, Shimadzu Corp., Japan).

Reagents and Materials

Bilastine and Montelukast sodium samples from SYMED LABS LTD. in Hyderabad, India were chemically pure and concentrated. The Tablet formulation had the marked units of 20 mg Bilastine and 10 mg Montelukast sodium (Belatin-M Tablet, SYNOKEM Pharmaceuticals Ltd., India), and these marked units were used for study. As a reagent, analytical grade methanol (E. Merck, Mumbai, India) was used.

FORMULATION OF STANDARD STOCK SOLUTION

It was done accurately to measure 10 mg of MONT and 10 mg of BILA apiece. These solutions were then transferred to two distinct 100 ml volumetric flasks, each of which contained a small amount of methanol and were used to create the stock solution. The flasks were shaken and

swirled in order to save the solids. Volumes that were labeled with methanol allowed for the 100 g/ml concentration of both compounds.

ABSORBANCE CORRECTION METHOD

The absorbance correction method makes use of the absorbance at two chosen wavelengths, one at the medication's maximum absorbance when another drug also exhibits significant absorbance, and the other being the wavelength where the first drug exhibits virtually no absorbance. Working standard solutions of MONT (8 g/ml) and BILA (16 g/ml) were made from the stock solutions using the proper dilution, and the full UV spectrum was scanned to identify the relevant wavelengths. Max values for MONT and BILA are 344 nm and 252 nm, respectively. At 252 nm, both medicines were found to have significant absorbance, but at 344 nm, only MONT showed absorption. The chosen wavelengths for analysis were 252 nm for BILA and 345 nm for MONT, as indicated in (Figure 3). The absorbance of the standard solutions was measured at 344 nm and 252 nm, with concentrations ranging from 2 to 12 g/ml of MONT and 4 to 24 g/ml of BILA, respectively. Plotting absorbance against the matching medication concentration produced a calibration curve. The following equations were used to determine the concentration of two medications in the sample solution:

$$C_{MONT} = A_1 / ax_1 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$C_{BILA} = A_2 - ax_2 C_{MONT} / ay_2 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where, A_1 and A_2 are the absorbance of mixture at 344 nm and 252 nm respectively,

ax_1 and ax_2 are absorptivities of MONT at 344 nm and 252 nm respectively,

ay_2 is absorptivity of BILA at 252 nm,

Figure 3: Covered Range spectra of MONT and BILA

GRADATION CURVES FOR MONT AND BILA

Final concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 g/ml of MONT and 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 g/ml of BILA, respectively, were obtained by combining suitable samples of the MONT and BILA working standard mixes with methanol at a specific mark. The range of solutions was analyzed between 400 and 200 nm. The absorbance of solutions was measured at 344 and 252 nm against methanol as a blank before being plotted versus concentrations. After that, the characteristics of A1 cm 1% were obtained, and two linear equations for two different compounds were assessed.

Figure 4: Calibration Curve of BILA at 252 nm

Figure 5: Calibration Curve of MONT at 344 nm

VALIDATION

PRECISION

For MONT and BILA estimates, various methods can be used. One of them involves estimating MONT (6, 8, and 10 g/ml) and BILA (12, 16, and 20 g/ml) three times on the same day and three times on three different days for three different concentrations. RSD is the end effect of this. Repeated scanning and measurements of the absorbance of solutions (n = 6) for MONT (6 g/ml)

and BILA (12 g/ml) were used to test the instrument's accuracy. RSD (relative standard deviation) was computed.

ACCURACY

Recovery studies verified the method's accuracy. A known quantity of the raw materials Bilastine and Montelukast sodium was added to the previously-analyzed formulation, and the process was then carried out in accordance with the analysis of the formulation. It was calculated how much of each medication was found. Each concentration underwent three iterations of this process. The % RSD was calculated.

LIMIT OF DETECTION AND LIMIT OF QUANTITATION

Limit of quantitation is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be quantitatively determined with adequate precision and accuracy. Limit of detection is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value. The International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) recommended using the following equations to calculate the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) in order to determine the drug's limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ).

$$\text{LOD}=3.3\sigma/S$$

$$\text{LOQ}=10\sigma/S$$

Where, σ = the standard deviation of the response and S = slope of the calibration curve.

Assay of tablet formulation

Twenty tablets were weighed and then ground into a powder. In a 100 ml volumetric flask, 10 mg equivalent MONT powder and 20 mg equivalent BILA are weighed and transferred. Then, in the same flask, 50 cc of methanol were added and sonicated for 5 minutes. Whatmann paper was used to filter the solution into a separate flask (a 100 ml volumetric flask). The volume was made up using the same solvent up to the mark. A specific amount of the aliquot was transferred to a volumetric flask with a 10 ml capacity, and the volume was filled with methanol to give an 8 g/ml concentration of MONT and a 16 g/ml concentration of BILA. Equation was used to calculate the concentration after the estimation of absorbance at 344 nm and 252 nm (1 and 2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The suggested approaches were approved in accordance with ICH guidelines. The absorbance of MONT and BILA were plotted against their respective concentrations, and it was discovered that these plots were linear in the concentration ranges of 2–12 g/ml and 4–24 g/ml, respectively. For the simultaneous equation technique, the correlation coefficients for the two medicines were 0.9999 at 344 nm and 0.9999 at 252 nm. For both of the medications listed in Table 1, precision was determined as same day and different days fluctuations, and % RSD was discovered to be

less than 2. The method's accuracy was assessed at levels of 50%, 100%, and 150%. According to Table 2, the recovery percentage for this approach ranges from 99.33 to 100.34% for MONT and from 99.83 to 100.63% for BILA. For MONT and BILA, the LOD and LOQ are 0.21 and 0.63 and 0.43 and 1.32, respectively. The method can be utilised effectively to estimate MONT and BILA simultaneously in a combination tablet dosage form. Marketed tablets were examined, and the results ranged from 98 to 102% (Table 3).

Table 1. Validation Parameters for simultaneous equation method

Parameters	Montelukast Sodium	Bilastine
$\lambda_{max}(nm)$	344	252
Linearity range ($\mu g/ml$)	2-12	4-24
Correlation Coefficient	0.9999	0.9999
Precision	% RSD	
Repeatability	0.32%	0.35%
Intraday	0.18-0.80%	0.23-0.59%
Interday	0.18-0.29%	0.24-0.44%
% Recovery	99.33-100.34%	99.83-100.63%
LOD	0.21	0.43
LOQ	0.63	1.32

Table 2. % Recovery Studies for Montelukast Sodium and Bilastine

% Spiki	Conc. of taken (μg)	Conc. of added (μg)	Total ($\mu g/ml$)	Amt of found (μg)	Amt of recovered ($\mu g/ml$)	% Recove	Mean % Recd SD
Montelukast Sodium							
50	4	2	6	6.07	4.07	101.17	100.34 $\pm$ 1.892969
	4	2	6	5.89	3.89	98.17	
	4	2	6	6.10	4.10	101.67	
100	4	4	8	8.05	4.05	100.62	99.33 $\pm$

	4	4	8	7.90	3.90	98.75	1.119062
	4	4	8	7.89	3.89	98.62	
150	4	6	10	10.10	4.10	101.00	100.23 ±
	4	6	10	9.98	3.98	99.80	0.665833
	4	6	10	9.99	3.99	99.90	
Bilastine							
50	8	4	12	12.02	8.02	100.17	99.83 ±
	8	4	12	11.97	7.97	99.75	0.303699
	8	4	12	11.95	7.95	99.58	
100	8	8	16	16.09	8.09	100.56	99.87 ±
	8	8	16	15.91	7.91	99.43	0.605062
	8	8	16	15.94	7.94	99.62	
150	8	12	20	19.97	7.97	99.85	100.63 ±
	8	12	20	20.03	8.03	101.50	0.828151
	8	12	20	20.11	8.11	100.55	

Table 3. Assay of marketed formulation (n=3)

Drug name	Labelled claim	Conc. taken (µg)	Conc. found (µg)	% Assay ± SD
Montelukast Sodium	10	8	8.03	100.33% ± 0.069282
Bilastine	20	16	16.2	101.4% ± 0.363731

CONCLUSION:

For the determination and estimation of the MONT and BILA together, the simultaneous equation method has developed. The technique produces a simple, effective, explicit, and definite result. In comparison to other chromatographic separation procedures, the absorption

correction technique is simple, less time-consuming, and cost-effective for analysis. The same method is effectively used to estimate the combined dosage for MONT and BILA.

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